

Regenerative Responses of Tropical CIMMYT Maize Lines (*Zea Mays L.*) by Indirect Organogenesis and Somatic Embryogenesis: A Novel Method with Silver Sulfate

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Abstract-: The goal of this research was to regenerate the entire plant by somatic embryogenesis utilizing immature zygotic embryos (IZE) as explants. Furthermore, the histomorphological structures of embryogenic cells and tissues were investigated under a microscope. The maize genotypes (CML 406, CML 419, CML 424, 425, and CML 427) were received from CIMMYT. Among the several media screened for optimum callus induction, N6 salts and vitamins was determined as the best. The optimized auxin, organic and inorganic additives were 9 μM of 2, 4-D, 200 mg/L casein hydrolysate, 17.4 mM L-Proline and 50 μM Ag_2SO_4 . The frequencies of callus initiation were 51.67%, 77.67%, 62.22% and 85.56% for CML 406, CML 419, CML 425 and CML 427 respectively. The percentage of the embryogenic callus formed in cultures containing Ag_2SO_4 was ranged between 10.4 and 12.8 in CML 419 and 427 lines, respectively. In media containing AgNO_3 , the percentage of the embryogenic callus was 7.6 and 9.4 in CML 419 and 427 correspondingly. CML 406 and 425 did not produce more than 2% of embryogenic callus. Furthermore, media with silver chloride yielded only about 3% of embryonic callus in the responsive lines. Embryogenic calli were maintained in the same media devoid of all silver salts under dark condition. The optimum medium for germination of somatic embryo was found to be hormone-free half MS. On the other hand, MS media containing 10 μM kinetin gave highest indirect organogenic response. In both protocols, NAA at a concentration of 5 μM was determined as an ideal hormone for root induction in MS medium. SEM and TEM micrographs revealed morphogenesis of somatic embryos from globular to torpedo-shape.

Keywords: Immature Zygotic Embryo, Regeneration, Silver Sulphate, Somatic embryogenesis, *Zea mays*

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1.0 Introduction

In *in vitro* tissue culture of plants, there exist virtually three developmental pathways through which plants could be regenerated. These pathways are somatic embryogenesis, organogenesis (usually shoot) and Propagation from pre-existing meristems (shoot or nodal culture). In maize tissue culture, the first two protocols are widely used. Somatic embryogenesis can be defined as the phenomena in which somatic cells evolve into plant via stages peculiar to embryological development in the absence of zygote formation. In another word, somatic embryogenesis is asexual embryogenesis since it does not require fusion of gametes. It has been over a half of a century since it was discovered that somatic embryos were produced when carrot cells were cultured *in vitro* (Reinert 1958, Steward et al. 1958). Ever since, a considerable amount of information has

been on the increase. Interestingly, the development of somatic embryos was shown to be intimately correlated to that of zygotic embryos, both morphological and otherwise (Zimmerman 1993). In the olden days, it was thought that transition of somatic cells to embryogenic tissues, neither happens naturally nor spontaneously, but induced. However, that notion could not be sustained when it was shown that embryogenesis can as well emerge from isolated somatic or gametic cells naturally as in leaf edges of *Kalanchoe*' (Dodeman et al. 1997). Previous reports on plant regeneration via somatic embryogenesis on the three most important cereal crops are maize (Armstrong and Green 1985, Lu et al. 1982, Lu et al. 1983, Vasil et al. 1984, Vasil et al. 1985), rice (Abdullah et al. 1986, Chen et al. 1985, Siriwardana and Nabors 1983) and wheat (Galiba and Yamada 1988, Ozias-Akins and Vasil 1983, Scott et al. 1990). Adventitious organogenesis refers to propagation of organs from explants without pre-

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existing meristems. Adventitious formation of shoots is referred to as caulogenesis and of roots as rhizogenesis. Gahan and George (2008) have categorized adventitious organogenesis as theoretically occur in either of two distinct processes. (1) Directly from the differentiated cells in a newly transferred piece of whole-plant tissue, without intermediate proliferation of undifferentiated tissue. (2) Indirectly from the unspecialized, unorganized and dedifferentiated cells of callus tissues or suspension cultures. Several indirect organogenesis in cereals including maize were reported. For example, Pathi et al. (2013) have obtained high frequency of compact granular organogenic callus from tropical maize lines with on MS medium supplemented with 2.5 mg/L 2,4-D and 1.5 mg/L BAP at light conditions. These callus was further regenerated on MS medium supplemented with 2.0 mg/L BAP, 1 mg/L kinetin & 0.5 mg/L NAA. Organogenic calli induced from shoot apices of Kenyan maize lines was also obtained in MS media with high BAP and 2,4-D concentration of 26.64 and 9.0 μ M respectively (Muoma et al., 2008). In the production of type II callus, Carvalho et al. (1997) observed that not all callus classified as embryogenic produced plants, and some classified as non-embryogenic produced plants as well.

Several organic and inorganic additives have been employed in *in vitro* culture of maize as well as other plant species with sole aim of increasing the frequency of somatic embryogenesis formation. The most popular organic additive employed for this purpose is L-proline (Armstrong and Green 1985). However, silver nitrate was adjudged as the most potent inducer of somatic embryogenesis. It was first reported to have increase the frequency of somatic embryo formation in maize (Duncan et al. 1985). Silver nitrate was also reported to enhance the production and regeneration of embryogenic type II callus in maize (Vain et al. 1989). In addition, silver nitrate was shown to effectively stimulate shoot regeneration in wheat (Purnhauser et al. 1987). These and indeed other influences of silver nitrate was attributed to the silver ions (Ag^+). Silver nitrate is slightly toxic, expensive usually non-autoclavable. On the contrary silver sulfate is less toxic, less expensive and can be autoclaved. The objectives of this study were 1) To investigate the regeneration capacities of these new lines with a view to exploiting their tissue culture and

transformation potentials, and 2) To evaluate the role of other salts of silver such as silver chloride and silver sulphate in addition to silver nitrate in induction of somatic embryogenesis.

2.0 Material and Method

Plant Materials

Seeds of tropical maize lines were supplied by International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center, popularly known as CIMMYT Mexico. The seeds of these lines (CML 406, CML 419, CML 424, 425 and CML 427) were grown under glasshouse condition located at the Serdang Campus of Universiti Putra Malaysia. Eleven to fifteen days after pollination of self-pollinated Ears were obtained. The ears that were not used immediately were preserved in the refrigerator up to three days. Harvested ears were dehusked and sterilized with 70% ethanol for one minute, rinsed 3-5 times with sterilized distilled water. Thereafter, ears were treated with commercial bleach (Clorox) containing 30 % (v/v) Sodium Hypochloride with or without 1-2 drops of tween 20 for fifteen minutes and repeated twice.

3.0

Callus Initiation and Maintenance

Media Optimization: Callus was initiated in five different media (B5 (Gamborg et al. 1968), LS (Linsmaier and Skoog 1965), MS (Murashige and Skoog 1962), N6 medium and vitamins (Chu et al. 1975) and lastly MS salts and B5 vitamins). These media were augmented with 4.5 μ M 2,4-D, The media with highest callusing frequency was subsequently for the evaluation of auxins.

Auxins Optimization: Optimum media was supplemented with different auxins at 5 μ M each. These auxins include: (2, 4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4-D), 3, 6-dichloro-2-methoxybenzoic acid (Dicamba), Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), Indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), 1-Naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), and Picloram). The best auxin was further optimized by varying its concentration from 0-25 μ M.

Evaluation of Silver Salts: After optimization of media and auxins for outstanding callus initiation; silver nitrate, silver sulphate and silver chloride were evaluated for somatic embryo formation. These were added singly in callus initiation media at concentration ranging between 10 and 100 μ M.

In all optimization and other studies, the media was augmented with 200 mg/L casein

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hydrolysate, 15 mM L-proline and 30 g/L sucrose. The pH of the media was adjusted to 5.75 and 3 g/L gelrite was added (5 g/L gelrite was used in silver salts containing media). The media was autoclaved at 121°C for 20 minutes. Immature embryos were excised with the help of a sterile scalpel blade and forceps and placed directly on callus induction media with embryonic axis facing the media. The culture plates were incubated in total darkness for both callus initiation and proliferation.

Parameters Studied: After three weeks of culture, the following parameters were recorded: Number of days for callus formation, callus initiation efficiency, callus score, callus color, callus texture and presence or absence somatic embryos. The callus obtained were removed and transferred onto fresh media lacking any silver salt but containing (0-10 µM) benzylaminopurine (BAP) and/or N₆-furfuryladenine (kinetin) for maintenance studies. Embryogenic tissue was maintained on this media and sub-cultured every 10-14 days.

Regeneration

Regeneration studies was conducted using two approaches; via somatic embryogenesis and indirect organogenesis. For regeneration through somatic embryogenesis, three grams of callus clumps containing somatic embryos were transferred to hormone free MS or N6. While regeneration by indirect organogenesis, same amount of callus with or without somatic embryos were transferred to same media augmented with BAP, kinetin or Thidiazuron (TDZ) at a concentration of 0-22.5 µM each. Regenerated plantlets were transferred to the same media with various concentrations of cytokinins for shoot multiplication. Shoots obtained were transferred to rooting media constituted with MS or N6 and 5 µM Indole-3-acetic acid or Naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA). After sufficient root system was established, the plants were transferred to pots containing equal mixture of vermiculite and soil for acclimatization. After acclimatizing for 2-3 weeks they were moved to glass house where they were grown to maturity.

auxins on the frequency of callus formation. ANOVA was also used to establish the effect of silver salts on the formation of embryogenic callus. The ten replicate values used were nested in the ANOVA model. The results are express in the form of mean ± S.E and n=10 Differences is considered to be statistically significant if the probability value, p-value is less than 0.05 (p<0.05).

4.0 Results and Discussion

Media evaluation demonstrated that these lines are best cultured in N6 media with percentage of callus induction up to 95% (Fig.1). The second highest callus producing media was MS with up 80%. LS media produced the lowest percentage of callus. Analysis of variance and LSD post-hoc analysis showed that there is significant difference in terms of callus initiation responses with respect to all but MS and MSB5 media which showed no significant difference. Figure 2 illustrate callus initiation responses of the five auxins tested, 2, 4-D and dicamba proved to be very effective in stimulating caulogenesis. They both showed similar callusing response which was between 75 and 96% in CMLs 419 and 427. IAA did not form any callus in CML 406, instead, the some of the cultured embryo germinated while other developed roots. The highest percent of callus form in media containing NAA was only 30% in while for Picloram it was 65% and the callus was watery and loose. Specifically, at 2, 4-D concentration of 9 µM callus formation efficiency was found to be 87% while dicamba at 4.5 µM yield 93% callus In CMLs 406 and 425, the frequency of callus was between 26 and 54 %. However in all circumstances, callus induction was found to be genotype dependent. Both 2, 4-D and dicamba haven been involve in the formation of somatic embryos.

4.0 Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using the statistical software IBM SPSS Statistics., version 22. Mixed model analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the effect of genotypes, media, and

Assessment of silver salts on the formation of

Figure.1: Influence of different media type supplemented with 1mg/l Dicamba on callus initiation frequencies of CMLs. Means with Different Letters Differs significantly at P≤ 0.05 using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). Vertical bars designate Standard Deviation of the means (n=30).

embryogenic callus showed that AgNO₃ at a 50 μM yield higher percent of somatic embryos (12% and 14.6%) for CML 419 and 427 respectively. The difference was statistically significant when compared with Ag₂SO₄ which yield 8% and 12.8% for CML 419 and 427 respectively. Silver sulphate at a concentration of 80 μM produced about 10% embryogenic callus in CML 419 while in CML 427, about 14% of embryogenic callus was obtained at a slightly higher concentration of 100 μM. Silver chloride on the hand did induce the production embryogenic callus but it is insignificant compared to the control group. Even the little one produced readily turned brown indicating its cytotoxic effect. Statistical analysis indicated that there was a significant difference in the formation of embryogenic callus among the genotypes with respect to the treatment.

Figure 3. Four weeks old callus induced in callus induction media supplemented with 50 μM Ag₂SO₄ (A-C) CML 419 (D-F) CML

Under ideal situation, embryo development in intact plant was always associated with endogenous hormone such as Indole3-acetic acid (IAA) or Indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) (Feher et al. 2003). However, in most circumstances endogenous auxins present in the explant may not suffice to induce somatic embryogenesis in

vitro cultures. Even though N6 media was found to be the suitable media for callus induction and proliferation but was ineffective when it comes to regeneration. This could be due their differences in nitrogen contents in form of nitrates and ammonium ions or due to sulphate ions. In either case, the noticeable differences in both callus initiation and plant regeneration was statistically different. Different types of explants have routinely use induce callus. Exogenous application of PGRs not only stimulate the formation of somatic embryogenesis but also augmented the concentration of the endogenous auxin in a synergistic manner. For example, it was shown that endogenous levels of IAA were significantly increased by the addition of exogenous 2, 4-D into the carrot cell cultures (Michalczuk et al. 1992, Michalczuk et al. 1992). Notwithstanding, in exceptional cases, some cells can form somatic embryo in intro culture conditions in a predictable and reliable process in the absence of PGRs. This situation is evidenced in the production of somatic embryos from carrot tissues in hormone-free medium (Smith and Krikorian 1988). Of the five major classes of phytohormones, only auxins, cytokinins and interplay between them have been reported to have great impact in modulating growth and development in an organized manner in both intact plant and *in vitro* cultures (Vasil and Thorpe 1994). It was demonstrated that stem cells of plants were originally created at the time of embryogenesis. Moreover, interactions between auxin and cytokinin has been known to regulate organogenesis in in vitro cultured plants (Skoog and Miller 1957).

Figure 2: Optimization of auxins for optimum callus initiation frequencies of CMLs. Means with Different Letters varies significantly at ρ ≤ 0.05 using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). Error bars denote Standard Deviation of the means (n=30).

The results of the present exploration revealed that only less than 5% of the callus were developed into somatic embryo directly, and the majority of the embryogenic callus were formed

after fourth subculture (Figure 3). This observed discrepancies could be due to the fact that during the first induction process the cells were beginning to dedifferentiate. During the dedifferentiation process, the competent cells were being prepared to by switching on relevant genes for somatic embryogenesis. For regeneration through somatic embryogenesis, it was recorded that approximately 2% of embryogenic callus was regenerated in hormone-free MS media. It was also recognized that majority of the callus lost their embryogenic competence. This loss of embryogenicity could be due to change of culture conditions such as withdrawal of auxins and exposure to light. On the other hand, relatively 13% of organogenic callus was regenerated via indirect organogenesis in media containing 4.6 μM kinetin. In 8.8 μM BAP, roughly 8% of cultured organogenic callus was regenerated. However, when the organogenic callus was transferred in media containing 9 μM TDZ, roughly 4% of the cultured callus was regenerated (Figure 4). Majority of plant regeneration in maize and indeed other monocots employs kinetin. BAP too was utilized in other genotypes. For example at 2.2 μM it was reported to be the optimum concentration for plantlet regeneration and multiple shoot formation through callus initiation from mature maize embryo culture (Huang and Wei 2004). When callus was formed via split-seed method, regeneration was also reported to be highest at BAP 4.4 μM . Multiple shoots was also recorded at this concentration (Al-Abed et al. 2006).

Figure 4: Organogenic callus in regeneration media, MS supplemented with 10 μM Kinetin. (ABC) First passage (D) Second Passage (E) Third Passage (F) Fourth passage. (Bar = 1

Generally, auxins exert substantial control over a number of processes which include cell proliferation, cell division and differentiation as well as zygotic embryogenesis in root stem cells (Friml et al. 2003, Weijers and Jürgens 2005). Categorically, those compounds mimicking the

action of natural plant hormones are classified as plant growth regulators (PGRs). To date, numerous PGRs have been synthesized with biochemical activity which is comparable to that of natural hormones. In most cases, PGRs activity surpassed that of endogenous hormones (Davies 2010). Mechanistically, auxins like IAA mediate communications between organs, tissues and cells across remote distances, such as shoot and root apex. The interactions may also occur across very short ranges, in adjoining cells (Morris et al. 2010).

Auxin analogues are regarded as the most powerful PGRs in modulating the somatic embryogenesis in *in vitro* cultures. In most instances, embryogenic tissues consist of aggregate of embryogenic cells and non embryogenic ones as indicated in Fig 1 and 2. Even though dicamba was found to be effective in inducing somatic embryogenesis in these inbred lines, 2, 4-D was regarded as the most efficient in somatic embryogenesis induction in majority of tissue culture projects reported. Additionally, it was postulated that at certain concentration, 2, 4-D act as stress inducer either alone or indirectly through IAA metabolism (Pasternak et al. 2000).

In vitro cell cultures can be established from a number of explants. The most preferable one being undifferentiated cells usually from fast growing region (meristematic) such as shoots apical meristems (SAM), root apical meristems (RAM), immature zygotic embryo, buds etc. Cell cultures can also be initiated from dedifferentiated/mature organs. In cell/tissue culture, the inception of cell division and its subsequent sustenance is by no means a prelude to the determination of the destiny of explant (Feher et al. 2003). Early regeneration evidences from scanning electron microscopy showed emerging shoot primordia. These primordia undergoes independent segregation/differentiation. About two weeks after the onset of caulogenesis, root primordia begun to emanate. Adventitious roots formation ensued in same hormone-free media. However, when the plantlets were transferred to another media containing 5 μM NAA, roots proliferation proceeds at faster rate.

Meristematic activity induced by 2,4-D in the immature embryo led to the development of two distinct cell types, large vacuole cells in the

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abaxial parenchyma which are non embryogenic cells, and small, densely populated cells associated with the abaxial epidermis comprising of somatic embryos. After five to eight days of culture, the abaxial parenchyma underwent a series of periclinal divisions, producing files of cells which, together with the expansion of the palisade-like tissue, led to the rapid expansion of the abaxial epidermis due to high metabolic active and in the presence of 2,4-D this cells metamorphosed into a superficial meristem. The cells of this meristem were small, with large nuclei and densely staining cytoplasm, features associated with early embryogenic development. These cells gave rise to typical globular embryos. Somatic embryos of maize have also been reported to arise from deep-seated meristematic centers especially the scutella region (Armstrong and Green 1985).

5.0 Conclusion

From this study, it was clearly shown that genotypes plays a very crucial role in *in vitro* culture of Zea mays with respect callus initiation, formation of somatic embryogenesis and regeneration. Secondly Silver Sulphate could be used as replacement for silver nitrate. Due to the fact genotypes plays a crucial role in tissue culture, this new substance could have significance influence in other genotypes. This is because in all genotypes tested only two (CML 419 and 427) were able to produce somatic embryo. However, of these two, only CML 427 was regenerated via somatic embryogenesis. In conclusion, to the best of our knowledge, since the release of these lines, no any *in vitro* culture studies were reported on them. This study, may serve as a yardstick for further studies and improvement of this important crop especially in the field of genetic engineering.

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